

Origin of the Low Overpotential for Isopropanol Oxidation on Pt–Ru Electro catalysts

Alexander Simanenko, Pankaj Kumar Samal, Robert Hübsch, Jan Škvára, Juntao Yang, Maximilian Kastenmeier, Florian Winkler, Tomáš Skála, Nataliya Tsud, Sascha Mehl, Josef Mysliveček, Olaf Brummel,* Yaroslava Lykhach,* and Jörg Libuda*

Cite This: *ACS Energy Lett.* 2024, 9, 4875–4882

Read Online

ACCESS |

Metrics & More

Article Recommendations

Supporting Information

ABSTRACT: Electrochemically active liquid organic hydrogen carrier (EC-LOHC) technology is an emerging solution for safe and environmentally friendly hydrogen storage and energy conversion based on the use of organic redox-active compounds, such as the isopropanol/acetone couple. In this work, we identify the nature of the active state of the Pt–Ru electrocatalyst that provides the lowest overpotential and, thus, the highest catalytic activity. Toward this aim we employed *ex situ* electrochemical synchrotron radiation photoelectron spectroscopy (SRPES) and scanning tunneling microscopy (STM) in combination with *in situ* electrochemical infrared reflection absorption spectroscopy (EC-IRRAS). We show that the lowest overpotentials are not observed for Pt–Ru surface alloys but only in the presence of ultrasmall metallic Pt aggregates formed by dealloying of Pt–Ru catalysts upon oxidation and reduction cycles between 0.0 and 1.5 V_{RHE} . By tuning the initial composition of the Pt–Ru surface alloy, we maximize the density of active Pt aggregates.

The increasing availability of green electrical energy from renewable sources requires efficient energy storage and conversion technologies to manage temporal fluctuations in the power generation and demand. New strategies have emerged to address this challenge involving the use of liquid organic hydrogen carriers (LOHCs).^{1–5} The conventional LOHC concept involves the reversible catalytic hydrogenation and dehydrogenation of an organic compound.^{1–5} The current state-of-the-art in the conventional LOHC approach is the H0/H18-dibenzyltoluene (DBT) couple, a liquid hydrocarbon that is also used as a heat-transfer fluid.^{3,4} The concept allows hydrogen to be stored for long periods of time and transported over long distances in liquid form at room temperature and ambient pressure using existing petroleum infrastructure.⁴ However, there are challenges associated with converting the chemical energy stored in LOHCs back to electrical energy. First, the hydrogen gas must be produced in a dehydrogenation reactor.⁶ Second, the hydrogen must be converted to electricity using a proton-exchange membrane fuel cell (PEM-FC).⁶ The corresponding two-stage process is technically complex, expensive, space-consuming, and requires the handling of gaseous hydrogen, which demands additional safety measures. Importantly, the endothermic dehydrogenation reaction requires temperatures

much higher (>290 °C for DBT against 1.5 bar H_2) than the operating temperatures of the fuel cell (low-temperature PEM-FC ≤ 80 °C, high-temperature PEM-FC ≤ 180 °C).⁷ This temperature difference makes heat integration difficult and results in a significant loss of efficiency.^{6,8,9}

The concept of electrochemically active LOHCs (EC-LOHCs) circumvents the challenges associated with the conventional LOHC concept.^{6,10–12} An EC-LOHC can be used directly in fuel cells where it is selectively oxidized to its hydrogen-lean form, yielding electrons and protons.^{6,10–12} The most promising EC-LOHC system is the isopropanol/acetone redox couple.^{6,10,11,13–15} Both isopropanol and acetone are liquid compounds that can be readily separated and recharged. Compared to alternative fuels such as methanol or formic acid, the isopropanol fuel cell does not generate significant amounts of CO_2 .^{6,10} However, the hydrogen storage capacity of the

Received: July 23, 2024

Revised: August 26, 2024

Accepted: September 5, 2024

Published: September 17, 2024

Figure 1. Electronic structure of the Pt–Ru alloy model electrocatalysts as a function of composition (see Supporting Information, Section S1, for details): A gallery of the Pt–Ru surface alloy structures (a); The joint Ru 4s and Pt 4f (top row) and the joint Ru 3d and C 1s (bottom row) spectra obtained from Ru(0001) single crystal (left column), 0.5 ML Pt–Ru alloy model catalysts (middle column), and 3 ML Pt film (right column) supported on Ru(0001) (b). The joint Ru 4s and Pt 4f and the joint Ru 3d and C 1s spectra were acquired with photon energies of 180 and 380 eV, respectively.

isopropanol/acetone couple is lower than that of conventional LOHCs such as H0/H18-DBT. To address this challenge, Sievi et al. proposed a solution based on the use of the conventional LOHC couple as the main storage system combined with the EC-LOHC couple via transfer hydrogenation.¹⁰ Such a coupling strategy circumvents the temperature difference between the dehydrogenation reactor and the fuel cell resulting in a substantial improvement in efficiency from $\leq 38\%$ to over 50%.¹⁰

A particular challenge associated with EC-LOHC technology is the development of suitable catalysts for isopropanol fuel cells.^{6,10,13} At present, bimetallic Pt–Ru catalysts are the state-of-the-art for isopropanol oxidation due to their high resistance

to acetone poisoning and high activity.^{6,10,13} Khanipour et al. found that Pt–Ru catalysts have a characteristic low overpotential peak for isopropanol oxidation with an onset at 0.05 V_{RHE} .¹³ Notably, this value is ~ 0.25 V lower than that of Pt catalysts.^{6,10,13} However, the origin of the high activity of Pt–Ru catalysts remains elusive.^{6,13} In our previous work, we have shown that the high activity of Pt–Ru alloys is not associated with partial poisoning by CO (as in the case of H_2 and methanol PEM-FCs).¹⁰ It has also been shown that the activity of Pt–Ru is sensitive to the alloy composition and electrochemical treatment. It has been speculated that the high activity of Pt–Ru catalysts is related to specific structural

Figure 2. Stability of the Pt–Ru alloy model catalyst as a function of applied potential: Joint Ru 4s and Pt 4f (a) and the joint Ru 3d and C 1s (b) spectra obtained from 0.5 ML of Pt–Ru alloy model catalyst as a function of applied potential. The spectra obtained from as-prepared samples are shown at the top. Schematic representation of the dealloying procedure on the Pt–Ru alloy model catalyst (c). The Ru 4s, Pt 4f and Ru 3d, C 1s spectra were acquired with photon energies of 180 and 380 eV, respectively.

motifs on the electrode surface.¹³ However, the nature of these highly active sites has not yet been identified.

In this paper, we reveal the nature of the active state of the Pt–Ru alloy catalysts responsible for the electro-oxidation of isopropanol at low potentials. Most importantly, we demonstrate that it is possible to prepare surfaces completely dominated by these highly active sites. In our study, we follow a surface science approach which involves the use of well-defined Pt–Ru surface alloys of different compositions prepared on a Ru(0001) substrate in ultrahigh vacuum (see a gallery of Figure 1a). The thickness of the model Pt–Ru surface alloys is limited to one atomic monolayer. The preparation method of the Pt–Ru surface alloys has been studied in great detail by H. Hoster and R.J. Behm.^{16,17} The details of the preparation procedure of these model systems are given in Supporting Information, Section S1. The analysis of the electronic structure and morphology of the model Pt–Ru

surface alloys requires analytical methods which provide high surface sensitivity.¹⁸

The surface composition of the model catalysts was characterized by synchrotron radiation photoelectron spectroscopy (SRPES) coupled with an *ex situ* emission electrochemical cell. A selection of core level spectra obtained from pure Ru(0001) (left column), from the well-defined Pt–Ru surface alloy (middle column), and from a 3 monolayer (ML) thick Pt film (right column) are shown in Figure 1b. On the pure Ru(0001) surface, we observed two Ru 3d doublets at 279.7 eV (Ru 3d_{5/2} component, blue) and 280.1 eV (Ru 3d_{3/2}, green) associated with surface and bulk contributions, respectively.^{19,20} In addition, a broad contribution from a Ru 4s peak at 74.7 eV emerges in the Pt 4f region. The spectra obtained from the Pt–Ru surface alloy reveal a significant attenuation of the Ru 3d and Ru 4s signals and the emergence of a Pt 4f doublet peak at 71.1 eV (Pt 4f_{7/2}, green), which is attributed to Pt in the surface alloy.²¹ For the 3 ML Pt film,

Figure 3. High activity of Pt–Ru model catalyst for isopropanol oxidation after dealloying: STM images (141 nm × 141 nm) (a, e), cyclic voltammograms (b, c, d), s-polarized IRRA spectra (f, h), and intensity evolution of peak for the carbonyl band at 1697 cm^{-1} as a function of applied potential (g) obtained from the Pt–Ru alloy model catalyst before (a, d, f, g), during (c), and after (d, e, g, h) dealloying procedure. IRRA reference spectra were recorded at 0.05 V_{RHE} .

two Pt 4f doublet peaks emerge at 70.6 eV (Pt 4f_{7/2}, light blue) and 71.1 eV (Pt 4f_{5/2}, blue) associated with surface and bulk contributions, respectively.^{22,23} On this sample, the Ru signals are strongly attenuated by the Pt film, and we observed small additional signals from carbon resulting from the lengthy sample preparation (C 1s contributions in gray and additional component in the Pt 4f spectra, see Supporting Information, Section S1, for experimental details).^{24–28} The Ru 3d and Pt 4f spectra obtained from the Pt–Ru alloy model catalysts with different compositions are given in the Supporting Information (Section S2). Note that the compositions of the Pt–Ru surface alloys are indicated based on the nominal Pt coverage on the Ru(0001) substrate.

First, we investigated the stability of the well-defined 0.5 ML Pt–Ru alloy catalyst as a function of applied potential upon emersion from 0.2 M isopropanol in 0.1 M HClO₄ electrolyte (pH = 1). The experimental procedure is described in detail in Supporting Information (Section S1). The corresponding joint Ru 3s and Pt 4f and the joint Ru 3d and C 1s spectral regions are plotted in Figure 2. Emersion of the 0.5 ML Pt–Ru alloy at 0.0 V_{RHE} resulted in the appearance of a high-intensity feature in the Pt 4f spectrum at 71.6 eV (Pt 4f_{7/2}) and the disappearance of the surface Ru contribution in the joint Ru 3d region (see Figures 2a and 2b). The observed scenario is consistent with the adsorption of carbonaceous deposits associated with the C 1s contribution at 284.0 eV. Therefore, we assign the Pt 4f contribution at 71.6 eV (Pt 4f_{7/2}) to the

formation of Pt⁰–C bonds. The corresponding peak decreases with increasing potential below 0.9 V_{RHE} (Figure 2a). We assume that the origin of the carbonaceous deposits is most likely related to the accumulation of adventitious carbon during sample transfer and immersion. Between 0.9 and 1.2 V_{RHE}, we observed a partial removal of carbon from the Pt sites leading to an increase in the Pt⁰/Pt⁰–C ratio from ~0.2 at 0.0 V_{RHE} to ~2.5 at 1.2 V_{RHE} (Supporting Information, Section S3, Figure S2c). Carbon removal from Pt sites is triggered by oxidation when hydroxyl groups and surface oxide are formed in this potential range.^{14,29,30} In the potential range up to 1.2 V_{RHE}, the Ru 3d core level spectra contain only a bulk contribution from metallic Ru. Note, however, that the onset of Ru oxidation is strongly dependent on the Pt coverage and shifts to lower potentials with decreasing Pt coverage (Figure S5).

Increasing the potential beyond 1.2 V_{RHE} caused oxidation of the surface. We assign the corresponding peaks at 72.1 eV (Pt 4f_{7/2}) to the Pt²⁺ state in PtO (Figure 2a) and at 280.8 eV (Ru 3d_{5/2}) to RuO_x (Figure 2b). Upon returning to 0.0 V_{RHE}, we observed a reduction of both metal oxides to metallic Pt⁰ and Ru⁰ states.

Most interestingly, however, the corresponding Pt⁰ contribution reappeared, but was shifted by 0.3 eV with respect to the Pt–Ru alloy at 71.3 eV (Pt 4f_{7/2}). In addition, the full width at half-maximum (FWHM) of the Pt 4f peak now increased from 0.7 to 1.0 eV. The observed behavior suggests that there is a dealloying process triggered by electrochemical oxidation and reduction of the Pt–Ru alloy.^{31,32} The shift in the Pt 4f binding energy and the increase in the FWHM of the metallic Pt contribution indicate the formation of ultrasmall Pt aggregates (see Supporting Information, Section S4, for detailed discussion).³³ We conclude that cycling between 0.0 and 1.5 V_{RHE} leads to the formation of ultrasmall Pt aggregates on the surface of Ru(0001). The process is illustrated schematically in Figure 2c. In the following, we refer to the corresponding electrochemical treatment that leads to the formation of Pt aggregates as the “dealloying procedure”.

In the next step, we subjected Pt–Ru surface alloys of different compositions to the dealloying procedure and investigated the catalytic activity of these samples. Specifically, we prepared Pt–Ru surface alloys with Pt coverages between 0.05 and 0.75 ML of Pt and a 3 ML thick Pt film. All samples, including the reference Ru(0001), were studied by cyclic voltammetry (CV, 10 mV·s⁻¹) at potentials between 0.0 and 0.9 V_{RHE} in 0.2 M isopropanol in 0.1 M HClO₄ (pH 1) electrolyte before and after dealloying (0.0–1.5 V_{RHE}, 10 mV·s⁻¹). The complete set of CVs and the corresponding core level spectra obtained from the studied samples are discussed in detail in the Supporting Information (Section S5).

The most striking results were obtained on the sample with 0.125 ML Pt coverage; see Figure 3b–d. Prior to the dealloying procedure, the onset of isopropanol oxidation occurs around 0.5 V_{RHE} with the peak maximum at ~0.75 V_{RHE} (Figure 3b). As the number of cycles increased, the intensity of the oxidation peak decreased due to poisoning of the active sites by adsorbed acetone.^{13,14} During the course of the dealloying procedure, we observed a gradual transformation of the high-potential peak into a low-potential peak with an onset potential at 0.05 V_{RHE} and a peak maximum at ~0.15 V_{RHE} (Figure 3c). The conversion is completed after the third cycle. We note that after the dealloying procedure was completed (Figure 3d), the low-potential peak at 0.15 V_{RHE} was the only

feature present in the CV. Our observation suggests that after dealloying, the surface is completely covered by Pt aggregates and that these aggregates show slower deactivation due to poisoning¹⁴ than the well-ordered Pt–Ru alloy.

The morphological changes induced by the dealloying procedure were verified by UHV scanning tunneling microscopy (STM) coupled with an *ex situ* emersion electrochemical cell (see Supporting Information, Section S1 for details). The STM images of the 0.1 ML Pt–Ru surface alloy before and after the dealloying procedure are shown in Figure 3a and 3e, respectively. The STM images of the clean Ru(0001) single crystal surface and the Pt–Ru surface alloy are shown in Figure S7. Before the dealloying procedure, the morphology of the well-ordered Pt–Ru alloy is well preserved upon cycling between 0.0 and 0.9 V_{RHE} (Figure 3a). In particular, we observed flat terraces covered by a few small aggregates. We attribute the latter to residual carbon and electrolyte. In contrast, the dealloying procedure induced strong morphological changes. We observed significant surface roughening and the formation of clusters with an apparent size of 5–10 nm (Figure 3e). This observation is consistent with the dealloying process, which results in a rough Ru surface and ultrasmall Pt aggregates.

Finally, we followed isopropanol oxidation before and after the dealloying procedure by *in situ* electrochemical infrared reflection absorption spectroscopy (EC-IRRAS) to verify that the observed current densities correspond to the conversion of isopropanol to acetone. This was necessary because the low-potential isopropanol oxidation peak at 0.15 V_{RHE} overlaps with the hydrogen and OH adsorption and desorption region between 0.05 and 0.4 V_{RHE}.¹⁶ The evolution of the IR spectra obtained from the well-ordered Pt–Ru alloy with a Pt coverage of roughly 0.5 ML (see Supporting Information, Section S1, for details) before and after the dealloying procedure is shown in Figures 3f and 3h, respectively. The spectra were recorded during a linear potential increase with s-polarized (Figure 3f, h) and p-polarized IR light (Figure S8); see Supporting Information for details. Briefly, all IR spectra are difference spectra with respect to the reference spectrum obtained at 0.05 V_{RHE}. The negative bands (pointing down) indicate species being formed, while the positive bands (pointing up) indicate species being consumed. For EC-IRRAS on metallic substrates, p-polarized bands correspond to species adsorbed on the surface as well as species dissolved in solution, and s-polarized bands correspond to species exclusively dissolved in solution.^{34,35} For reference, the attenuated total reflectance (ATR) spectra of isopropanol and acetone in the spectral region between 1100 and 2500 cm⁻¹ are shown in the upper panels of Figures 3f and 3h.

For both samples, we observe positive bands at 1467, 1387, 1306, 1165, and 1129 cm⁻¹, which we assign to the $\delta_{\text{asym}}(\text{CH}_3)/\delta_{\text{sym}}(\text{CH}_3)$, $\nu(\text{C}-\text{C})$, $\delta(\text{O}-\text{H})$, $\nu(\text{C}-\text{C})$ and $\nu(\text{C}-\text{O})$ vibrational modes of the consumed isopropanol.¹⁴ Simultaneously, negative bands appear at 1697, 1370, and 1240 cm⁻¹, which we assign to the $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$, $\delta_{\text{sym}}(\text{CH}_3)/\nu_{\text{asym}}(\text{C}-\text{C})$ and $\nu_{\text{asym}}(\text{C}-\text{C})$ vibrational modes of the formed acetone.¹⁴ All band positions are in good agreement with the band positions reported in previous works.^{14,36} Besides these, we observe a minor band at 2343 cm⁻¹ that is characteristic for the $\nu(\text{CO}_2)$ vibration. The corresponding band appears at potentials above about 0.5 V_{RHE} and has an extremely low intensity on both samples. This indicates that only very small traces of CO₂ are formed, which were observed previously also

on other Pt surfaces.^{14,37–39} Importantly, we do not observe any bands assigned to the catalyst poison CO_{ads} which we would expect to see between 2100 and 1750 cm^{-1} in the spectra measured in p-polarization (Figure S8).⁴⁰ Note that with EC-IRRAS we would be able to detect surface coverages even below 1% of a monolayer of CO_{ads} . This observation indicates that CO_2 is formed following a reaction channel which does not involve CO_{ads} .

While isopropanol is converted to acetone with very high selectivity before and after dealloying, the reaction occurs at completely different potentials (Figure 3g). Before dealloying, we observed only traces of acetone formation in the potential window between 0.1 and 0.3 V_{RHE} , which we attribute to small amounts of Pt aggregates already present after preparation. Note that this type of sample also shows a shoulder in this potential range by cyclic voltammetry (Figure S3e). However, the main conversion takes place between 0.3 and 0.9 V_{RHE} , i.e., in the potential window assigned to isopropanol oxidation on Pt surfaces. After dealloying, we observe a pronounced increase in conversion between 0.08 and 0.2 V_{RHE} , while at higher potentials, the sample shows no conversion. The corresponding changes are better seen in the additional spectra shown in the Supporting Information (Figure S9). This demonstrates that the formation of small Pt aggregates induced by the dealloying procedure quantitatively converts the surface from low activity to a state with very high activity, i.e. low overpotential. The comparison of the IRRAS spectra obtained in s- (species in solution only) and p-polarization (adsorbed species and species in solution) indicates that acetone is the main poisoning agent (see Supporting Information, Figure S10). However, the extent of poisoning is less pronounced in the presence of ultrasmall Pt aggregates.

The promotional role of Ru in the Pt–Ru alloys is typically associated with facile water activation at Ru sites and transfer of oxygen to Pt sites.^{41–43} However, our study shows that after dealloying of the Pt–Ru alloys, the additional role of Ru is to stabilize ultrasmall Pt aggregates against sintering. The corresponding dealloying procedure does not require the presence of isopropanol in solution and can be effectively performed in a blank electrolyte (data not shown). This is in agreement with the study of Kormányos et al., who found that the isopropanol has no significant effect on the dissolution behavior of Pt and Ru in commercial PtRu alloys in the potential region where dealloying occurs.⁴⁴

In conclusion, we identified the nature of the active sites responsible for the low overpotential in isopropanol oxidation on Pt–Ru alloys. We used a model approach that involves the preparation and characterization of well-defined Pt–Ru surface alloys under UHV conditions. The structural and compositional changes of these model electrocatalysts were investigated by SRPES and STM coupled with EC *ex situ* emersion cells. The electrochemical activity and selectivity were studied by CV and *in situ* EC-IRRAS. Our studies suggest that the active sites on Pt–Ru catalysts are not the Pt–Ru alloy ensembles but ultrasmall Pt aggregates supported on the Ru surface. These aggregates are formed when the Pt–Ru surface alloys are dealloyed by cycling between 0.0 and 1.5 V_{RHE} . We demonstrated that by dealloying we can convert the original alloy surface, which shows high overpotential for isopropanol oxidation (CV peak at 0.75 V_{RHE}), into a very active state (CV peak at 0.15 V_{RHE}). For the 0.125 ML Pt–Ru surface alloy, the low-overpotential peak is the only feature in the CV, suggesting that the surface is fully covered by highly active Pt aggregates.

The structure–activity correlation and dealloying procedure identified in this work may help to improve the preparation and reactivation procedures for electrocatalysts in EC-LOHC fuel cells.

■ ASSOCIATED CONTENT

Data Availability Statement

Source data are provided at Zenodo: [10.5281/zenodo.12720843](https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.12720843).

Supporting Information

The Supporting Information is available free of charge at <https://pubs.acs.org/doi/10.1021/acsenergylett.4c01987>.

Experimental procedures information, SRPES results of as-prepared samples and under electrochemical conditions, CV results of samples with different Pt coverage, STM results of as-prepared samples, EC-IRRAS in p-polarization results (PDF)

■ AUTHOR INFORMATION

Corresponding Authors

Olaf Brummel – Interface Research and Catalysis, ECRC, Friedrich-Alexander-Universität Erlangen-Nürnberg, 91058 Erlangen, Germany; orcid.org/0000-0001-5968-0774; Email: olaf.brummel@fau.de

Yaroslava Lykhach – Interface Research and Catalysis, ECRC, Friedrich-Alexander-Universität Erlangen-Nürnberg, 91058 Erlangen, Germany; orcid.org/0000-0003-3989-0365; Email: yaroslava.lykhach@fau.de

Jörg Libuda – Interface Research and Catalysis, ECRC, Friedrich-Alexander-Universität Erlangen-Nürnberg, 91058 Erlangen, Germany; orcid.org/0000-0003-4713-5941; Email: joerg.libuda@fau.de

Authors

Alexander Simanenko – Interface Research and Catalysis, ECRC, Friedrich-Alexander-Universität Erlangen-Nürnberg, 91058 Erlangen, Germany; orcid.org/0000-0001-5152-1533

Pankaj Kumar Samal – Charles University, Faculty of Mathematics and Physics, Department of Surface and Plasma Science, Prague 18000, Czech Republic

Robert Hübsch – Interface Research and Catalysis, ECRC, Friedrich-Alexander-Universität Erlangen-Nürnberg, 91058 Erlangen, Germany

Jan Škvára – Charles University, Faculty of Mathematics and Physics, Department of Surface and Plasma Science, Prague 18000, Czech Republic

Juntao Yang – Interface Research and Catalysis, ECRC, Friedrich-Alexander-Universität Erlangen-Nürnberg, 91058 Erlangen, Germany

Maximilian Kastenmeier – Interface Research and Catalysis, ECRC, Friedrich-Alexander-Universität Erlangen-Nürnberg, 91058 Erlangen, Germany; orcid.org/0000-0002-4532-8072

Florian Winkler – Interface Research and Catalysis, ECRC, Friedrich-Alexander-Universität Erlangen-Nürnberg, 91058 Erlangen, Germany

Tomáš Skála – Charles University, Faculty of Mathematics and Physics, Department of Surface and Plasma Science, Prague 18000, Czech Republic; orcid.org/0000-0003-2909-9422

Nataliya Tsud – Charles University, Faculty of Mathematics and Physics, Department of Surface and Plasma Science, Prague 18000, Czech Republic; orcid.org/0000-0001-7439-7731

Sascha Mehl – Elettra-Sincrotrone Trieste SCpA, Basovizza, Trieste 34149, Italy; orcid.org/0000-0002-0228-177X

Josef Mysliveček – Charles University, Faculty of Mathematics and Physics, Department of Surface and Plasma Science, Prague 18000, Czech Republic; orcid.org/0000-0003-2305-2711

Complete contact information is available at:
<https://pubs.acs.org/10.1021/acsenerylett.4c01987>

Notes

The authors declare no competing financial interest.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

The authors acknowledge the financial support from the Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft (DFG) via the Collaborative Research Centre SFB 1452 - Catalysis at Liquid Interfaces (Project 431791331) and the Bavarian Ministry of Economic Affairs, Regional Development and Energy. Additional support was given by the DFG via Projects 322419553, 431733372, 453560721, and 418603497 and the German Federal Ministry of Education and Research (BMBF, Project Combined Infrared and X-ray Analytics of Energy Materials, CIXenergy 05K19WE1). The authors further acknowledge the financial support of the Czech Science Foundation (GAČR, project 2021727X), and the Ministry of Education, Youth and Sports of the Czech Republic (MSMT, project QM4ST, reg. no. CZ.02.01.01/00/22_008/0004572; project LM2023072). The authors acknowledge the CERIC–ERIC Consortium for the access to experimental facilities and financial support. The authors thank Dr. Kevin Charles Prince for the support and organizing the beamtime. J. Y. acknowledges the support from the China Scholarship Council for the stay at the Friedrich-Alexander-Universität Erlangen-Nürnberg. J.Š. acknowledges the support of the Grant Agency of the Charles University (GAUK, project 199423).

REFERENCES

- (1) Teichmann, D.; Arlt, W.; Wasserscheid, P.; Freymann, R. A Future Energy Supply Based on Liquid Organic Hydrogen Carriers (LOHC). *Energy Environ. Sci.* **2011**, *4* (8), 2767.
- (2) Yadav, M.; Xu, Q. Liquid-Phase Chemical Hydrogen Storage Materials. *Energy Environ. Sci.* **2012**, *5* (12), 9698–9725.
- (3) Preuster, P.; Alekseev, A.; Wasserscheid, P. Hydrogen Storage Technologies for Future Energy Systems. *Annu. Rev. Chem. Biomol. Eng.* **2017**, *8*, 445–471.
- (4) Preuster, P.; Papp, C.; Wasserscheid, P. Liquid Organic Hydrogen Carriers (LOHCs): Toward a Hydrogen-Free Hydrogen Economy. *Acc. Chem. Res.* **2017**, *50* (1), 74–85.
- (5) Niermann, M.; Beckendorff, A.; Kaltschmitt, M.; Bonhoff, K. Liquid Organic Hydrogen Carrier (LOHC) - Assessment Based on Chemical and Economic Properties. *Int. J. Hydrogen Energy* **2019**, *44* (13), 6631–6654.
- (6) Brodt, M.; Müller, K.; Kerres, J.; Katsounaros, I.; Mayrhofer, K.; Preuster, P.; Wasserscheid, P.; Thiele, S. The 2-Propanol Fuel Cell: A Review from the Perspective of a Hydrogen Energy Economy. *Energy Technol.* **2021**, *9* (9), 2100164.
- (7) Jorschick, H.; Preuster, P.; Dürr, S.; Seidel, A.; Müller, K.; Bösmann, A.; Wasserscheid, P. Hydrogen Storage Using a Hot Pressure Swing Reactor. *Energy Environ. Sci.* **2017**, *10* (7), 1652–1659.

(8) Müller, K.; Thiele, S.; Wasserscheid, P. Evaluations of Concepts for the Integration of Fuel Cells in Liquid Organic Hydrogen Carrier Systems. *Energy Fuels* **2019**, *33* (10), 10324–10330.

(9) Prokop, M.; Drakselova, M.; Bouzek, K. Review of the Experimental Study and Prediction of Pt-Based Catalyst Degradation during PEM Fuel Cell Operation. *Curr. Opin. Electrochem.* **2020**, *20*, 20–27.

(10) Sievi, G.; Geburtig, D.; Skeledzic, T.; Bösmann, A.; Preuster, P.; Brummel, O.; Waidhas, F.; Montero, M. A.; Khanipour, P.; Katsounaros, I.; Libuda, J.; Mayrhofer, K. J. J.; Wasserscheid, P. Towards an Efficient Liquid Organic Hydrogen Carrier Fuel Cell Concept. *Energy Environ. Sci.* **2019**, *12* (7), 2305–2314.

(11) Cho, J.; Kim, B.; Venkateshalu, S.; Chung, D. Y.; Lee, K.; Choi, S., II Electrochemically Activatable Liquid Organic Hydrogen Carriers and Their Applications. *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2023**, *145* (31), 16951–16965.

(12) Tang, J.; Xie, R.; Pishva, P.; Shen, X.; Zhu, Y.; Peng, Z. Recent Progress and Perspectives of Liquid Organic Hydrogen Carrier Electrochemistry for Energy Applications. *J. Mater. Chem. A* **2024**, *12* (26), 15580–15591.

(13) Khanipour, P.; Speck, F. D.; Mangoufis-Giasin, I.; Mayrhofer, K. J. J.; Cherevko, S.; Katsounaros, I. Electrochemical Oxidation of Isopropanol on Platinum-Ruthenium Nanoparticles Studied with Real-Time Product and Dissolution Analytics. *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces* **2020**, *12* (30), 33670–33678.

(14) Waidhas, F.; Haschke, S.; Khanipour, P.; Fromm, L.; Görling, A.; Bachmann, J.; Katsounaros, I.; Mayrhofer, K. J. J.; Brummel, O.; Libuda, J. Secondary Alcohols as Rechargeable Electrofuels: Electro-oxidation of Isopropyl Alcohol at Pt Electrodes. *ACS Catal.* **2020**, *10* (12), 6831–6842.

(15) Hauenstein, P.; Mangoufis-Giasin, I.; Seeberger, D.; Wasserscheid, P.; Mayrhofer, K. J. J.; Katsounaros, I.; Thiele, S. Impact of Catalyst Loading, Ionomer Content, and Carbon Support on the Performance of Direct Isopropanol Fuel Cells. *J. Power Sources Adv.* **2021**, *10* (May), 100064.

(16) Hoster, H.; Richter, B.; Behm, R. J. Catalytic Influence of Pt Monolayer Islands on the Hydrogen Electrochemistry of Ru(0001) Studied by Ultrahigh Vacuum Scanning Tunneling Microscopy and Cyclic Voltammetry. *J. Phys. Chem. B* **2004**, *108* (38), 14780–14788.

(17) Hoster, H. E.; Bergbreiter, A.; Erne, P. M.; Hager, T.; Rauscher, H.; Behm, R. J. Pt_xRu_{1-x}/Ru(0001) Surface Alloys—Formation and Atom Distribution. *Phys. Chem. Phys.* **2008**, *10* (25), 3812.

(18) Rupperechter, G. Surface Science Approach to Heterogeneous Catalysis. *Surface and Interface Science* **2016**, *5*, 459–528.

(19) Godowski, P. J.; Onsgaard, J.; Ryszka, Z.; Rok, Ł.; Li, Z. S. Phase Transformations of the Pt/Ru(0001) Interface Studied by Photoemission. *Surf. Sci.* **2008**, *602* (2), 465–469.

(20) Starr, D. E.; Bluhm, H. CO Adsorption on PtRu/Ru(0001) Near Surface Alloys from Ultrahigh Vacuum to Millitorr Pressures. *J. Phys. Chem. C* **2014**, *118* (50), 29209–29217.

(21) Antolini, E.; Giorgi, L.; Cardellini, F.; Passalacqua, E. Physical and Morphological Characteristics and Electrochemical Behaviour in PEM Fuel Cells of PtRu/C Catalysts. *J. Solid State Electrochem.* **2001**, *5* (2), 131–140.

(22) Baetzold, R. C.; Apai, G.; Shustorovich, E.; Jaeger, R. Surface Core-Level Shifts for Pt Single-Crystal Surfaces. *Phys. Rev. B* **1982**, *26* (8), 4022–4027.

(23) Wakisaka, M.; Mitsui, S.; Hirose, Y.; Kawashima, K.; Uchida, H.; Watanabe, M. Electronic Structures of Pt-Co and Pt-Ru Alloys for CO-Tolerant Anode Catalysts in Polymer Electrolyte Fuel Cells Studied by EC-XPS. *J. Phys. Chem. B* **2006**, *110* (46), 23489–23496.

(24) Liu, Z.; Lee, J. Y.; Chen, W.; Han, M.; Gan, L. M. Physical and Electrochemical Characterizations of Microwave-Assisted Polyol Preparation of Carbon-Supported PtRu Nanoparticles. *Langmuir* **2004**, *20* (1), 181–187.

(25) Toyoshima, R.; Yoshida, M.; Monya, Y.; Suzuki, K.; Amemiya, K.; Mase, K.; Mun, B. S.; Kondoh, H. A High-Pressure-Induced Dense CO Overlay on a Pt(111) Surface: A Chemical Analysis

Using in Situ near Ambient Pressure XPS. *Phys. Chem. Chem. Phys.* **2014**, *16* (43), 23564–23567.

(26) Chen, X.; Wang, X.; Fang, D. A Review on C1s XPS-Spectra for Some Kinds of Carbon Materials. *Fullerenes, Nanotub. Carbon Nanostructures* **2020**, *28* (12), 1048–1058.

(27) Simanenko, A.; Kastenmeier, M.; Piliai, L.; Kosto, Y.; Skála, T.; Tsud, N.; Mehl, S.; Vorokhta, M.; Matolinová, I.; Lykhach, Y.; Libuda, J. Probing the Redox Capacity of Pt-CeO₂ Model Catalyst for Low-Temperature CO Oxidation. *J. Mater. Chem. A* **2023**, *11* (31), 16659–16670.

(28) Kastenmeier, M.; Fusek, L.; Mohamed, F.; Schuschke, C.; Ronovský, M.; Skála, T.; Farnesi Camellone, M.; Tsud, N.; Johánek, V.; Fabris, S.; Libuda, J.; Piccinin, S.; Lykhach, Y.; Mysliveček, J.; Brummel, O. Pd/Co₃O₄ (111) Interface Formation. *J. Phys. Chem. C* **2023**, *127* (12), 6034–6044.

(29) Schalenbach, M.; Kasian, O.; Ledendecker, M.; Speck, F. D.; Mingers, A. M.; Mayrhofer, K. J. J.; Cherevko, S. The Electrochemical Dissolution of Noble Metals in Alkaline Media. *Electrocatalysis* **2018**, *9* (2), 153–161.

(30) Eckl, M. J.; Mattausch, Y.; Jung, C. K.; Kirsch, S.; Schmidt, L.; Huebner, G.; Mueller, J. E.; Kibler, L. A.; Jacob, T. The Influence of Platinum Surface Oxidation on the Performance of a Polymer Electrolyte Membrane Fuel Cell—Probing Changes of Catalytically Active Surface Sites on a Polycrystalline Platinum Electrode for the Oxygen Reduction Reaction. *Electrochem. Sci. Adv.* **2022**, *2* (3), e2100049.

(31) Hengge, K.; Gänslar, T.; Pizzutilo, E.; Heinzl, C.; Beetz, M.; Mayrhofer, K. J. J.; Scheu, C. Accelerated Fuel Cell Tests of Anodic Pt/Ru Catalyst via Identical Location TEM: New Aspects of Degradation Behavior. *Int. J. Hydrogen Energy* **2017**, *42* (40), 25359–25371.

(32) Kormanyos, A.; Büttner, P.; Bosch, M.; Minichova, M.; Körner, A.; Jenewein, K. J.; Hutzler, A.; Mayrhofer, K. J. J.; Bachmann, J.; Cherevko, S. Stability of Bimetallic Pt x Ru y - From Model Surfaces to Nanoparticulate Electrocatalysts. *ACS Mater. Au* **2024**, *4* (3), 286–299.

(33) Zhou, W.-P.; Lewera, A.; Bagus, P. S.; Wieckowski, A. Electrochemical and Electronic Properties of Platinum Deposits on Ru(0001): Combined XPS and Cyclic Voltammetric Study. *J. Phys. Chem. C* **2007**, *111* (36), 13490–13496.

(34) Hoffmann, F. Infrared Reflection-Absorption Spectroscopy of Adsorbed Molecules. *Surf. Sci. Rep.* **1983**, *3* (2–3), 107.

(35) Iwasita, T.; Nart, F. In Situ Infrared Spectroscopy at Electrochemical Interfaces. *Prog. Surf. Sci.* **1997**, *55* (4), 271–340.

(36) Yang, T.; Kastenmeier, M.; Ronovský, M.; Fusek, L.; Skála, T.; Waidhas, F.; Bertram, M.; Tsud, N.; Matvija, P.; Prince, K. C.; Matolín, V.; Liu, Z.; Johánek, V.; Mysliveček, J.; Lykhach, Y.; Brummel, O.; Libuda, J. Selective Electrooxidation of 2-Propanol on Pt Nanoparticles Supported on Co₃O₄: An in-Situ Study on Atomically Defined Model Systems. *J. Phys. D: Appl. Phys.* **2021**, *54* (16), 164002.

(37) Pastor, E.; González, S.; Arvia, A. J. Electroreactivity of Isopropanol on Platinum in Acids Studied by DEMS and FTIRS. *J. Electroanal. Chem.* **1995**, *395* (1–2), 233–242.

(38) Sun, S.-G.; Lin, Y. Kinetics of Isopropanol Oxidation on Pt(111), Pt(110), Pt(100), Pt(610) and Pt(211) Single Crystal Electrodes -. *Electrochim. Acta* **1998**, *44* (6–7), 1153–1162.

(39) Mekazni, D. S.; Arán-Ais, R. M.; Herrero, E.; Feliu, J. M. On the Oxidation of Isopropanol on Platinum Single Crystal Electrodes. A Detailed Voltammetric and FTIR Study. *J. Power Sources* **2023**, *556*, 232396.

(40) Brummel, O.; Jacobse, L.; Simanenko, A.; Deng, X.; Geile, S.; Gutowski, O.; Vonk, V.; Lykhach, Y.; Stierle, A.; Libuda, J. Chemical and Structural In-Situ Characterization of Model Electrocatalysts by Combined Infrared Spectroscopy and Surface X-Ray Diffraction. *J. Phys. Chem. Lett.* **2023**, *14* (39), 8820–8827.

(41) Gasteiger, H. A.; Markovic, N.; Ross, P. N.; Cairns, E. J. Methanol Electrooxidation on Well-Characterized Platinum-Ruthenium Bulk Alloys. *J. Phys. Chem.* **1993**, *97* (46), 12020–12029.

(42) Gasteiger, H. A.; Marković, N.; Ross, P. N.; Cairns, E. J. Electro-Oxidation of Small Organic Molecules on Well-Characterized Pt–Ru Alloys. *Electrochim. Acta* **1994**, *39* (11–12), 1825–1832.

(43) Marković, N. M.; Gasteiger, H. A.; Ross, P. N.; Jiang, X.; Villegas, I.; Weaver, M. J. Electro-Oxidation Mechanisms of Methanol and Formic Acid on Pt-Ru Alloy Surfaces. *Electrochim. Acta* **1995**, *40* (1), 91–98.

(44) Kormányos, A.; Speck, F. D.; Mayrhofer, K. J. J.; Cherevko, S. Influence of Fuels and pH on the Dissolution Stability of Bifunctional PtRu/C Alloy Electrocatalysts. *ACS Catal.* **2020**, *10* (19), 10858–10870.